

SupportingInformationFile S4

Mathematica code for: Remodeling and the Evolution of Sexual Autonomy by Mate Choice

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This code presents a weak selection approximation analysis of the three-locus population-genetic model presented in the main text.

See Table 1 for definitions of alleles and key parameters.

*Note on parametrization: in the main text and Appendices S1–S3, we refer to the mutation parameter as "u" to avoid confusion with the subscript m used to denote male genotype frequencies. In the code below, the mutation parameter is denoted "m" and has been left as such to avoid the introduction of errors.

1. Develop the recursion equations for the model; Expand this cell to evaluate

In[]:=

```
ClearAll[st, sb, at, c,  $\gamma$ , m, init, T1B1R1, T2B1R1, T1B2R1, T2B2R1, T1B1R2,
T2B1R2, T1B2R2, T2B2R2, genotypes, r, msel, fsel, u, ab, z1, z2, zb, T2, B2,
R2, DTB, DTR, DBR, DTBR, Mating, s, mgenotypes, T21, B21, R21, DTB1, DTR1,
DBR1, DTBR1,  $\Delta$ T2,  $\Delta$ B2,  $\Delta$ R2,  $\Delta$ DTB,  $\Delta$ DTR,  $\Delta$ DBR,  $\Delta$ DTBR, perturb, sr, materec,
RecTable, MaskProb, ZygoteGenotypes, prob, zyg1, zyg2, zygoteProb];
```

```
(*three-
```

locus popgen model of Remodeling without direct costs to coercive mating*)

(*this model uses a probabilistic formulation for how females visit and mate at male territories. Females may either visit territories randomly or choose territories based on the kind of remodeling trait (bower) they see. Once there, the male may either coerce them into mating there without the opportunity to evaluate their display, or the female may choose the mate with that male (given that he has not already coerced her) by some factor related to his attractiveness.*)

(*There is a locus for male display trait $T2/T1$, remodeling trait (protective bower) $B2/B1$, and female preference for the type of Remodeling trait (bower), $R2/R1$. We make two underlying assumptions in this model: 1) that all males will coerce if they have the opportunity, and 2) that all females have a preference for attractive $T2$ males*)

(*parameters:

(1-st) is the fraction by which males having the $T2$ allele survive relative to Males having the $T1$ allele. (1-sb) is the fraction by which males having the $B2$ allele survive relative to Males having the $B1$ allele.

(1-sr) is the fraction by which females having the $R2$ allele survive relative to females having the $R1$ allele.

(a+1) is the factor by which attractive $T2$ allele males have a relative advantage in mating success over $T1$ males.

(ab+1) is the factor by which females with the $R2$ allele prefer to visit $B2$ bowers.

c is a number between 0 and 1 representing the rate of successful forced fertilization of a female, (or the likelihood of coercive attack) by a male without a protective bower ($B2$).

γ is a number between 0 and 1 representing the effectiveness of protective bowers at reducing a male's ability to coerce. If $\gamma=0$, then there is no effect, and if $\gamma=1$, then $B2$ males are unable to coerce, and females are free to choose the male based on his attractiveness once they are at his territory.

Lastly, we make an assumption of biased mutation at the T locus. This is meant as a proxy for a quantitative, multiallelic trait or some other process by which variation is maintained at the T locus, so that sexual selection is ongoing and we can explore the effects of sexual conflict over indirect effects in a simple population-genetic framework*)

(*recombination rate*)

$rtb = 1/2;$

```
rbr = 1 / 2;
```

```
(*solve for initial genotype frequencies*)
```

```
init = Solve[{T1B1R1 + T2B1R1 + T1B2R1 + T2B2R1 + T1B1R2 + T2B1R2 + T1B2R2 + T2B2R2 == 1,
  T2 == T2B1R1 + T2B2R1 + T2B1R2 + T2B2R2, B2 == T1B2R1 + T2B2R1 + T1B2R2 + T2B2R2,
  R2 == T1B1R2 + T2B1R2 + T1B2R2 + T2B2R2, DTB == (T2B2R1 + T2B2R2) - T2 * B2,
  DTR == (T2B1R2 + T2B2R2) - T2 * R2, DBR == (T1B2R2 + T2B2R2) - B2 * R2,
  DTBR == T2B2R2 - T2 * ((T1B2R2 + T2B2R2) - B2 * R2) -
  B2 * ((T2B1R2 + T2B2R2) - T2 * R2) - R2 * ((T2B2R1 + T2B2R2) - T2 * B2) - T2 * B2 * R2},
  {T1B1R1, T2B1R1, T1B2R1, T2B2R1, T1B1R2, T2B1R2, T1B2R2, T2B2R2}];
```

```
T1B1R1 = T1B1R1 /. init;
T2B1R1 = T2B1R1 /. init;
T1B2R1 = T1B2R1 /. init;
T2B2R1 = T2B2R1 /. init;
T1B1R2 = T1B1R2 /. init;
T2B1R2 = T2B1R2 /. init;
T1B2R2 = T1B2R2 /. init;
T2B2R2 = T2B2R2 /. init;
```

```
(*genotypes vector with initial allele frequencies and linkages*)
```

```
genotypes = Flatten[{T1B1R1, T2B1R1, T1B2R1, T2B2R1,
  T1B1R2, T2B1R2, T1B2R2, T2B2R2, T2, B2, R2, DTB, DTR, DBR, DTBR}];
```

```
(*set up the table of recombination probabilities that will yield the
  distribution of zygote genotypes resulting from each mated pairing*)
```

```
Nloci = 3;
Geno = 2 ^ Nloci;
masklim = 2 ^ (Nloci - 1);
recreate[1] = rtb;
recreate[2] = rbr;
```

```
(*Maskprob gives the probability for a particular pattern of
  recombination (a mask), based on given values of recombination
  rates between different loci ("recreate" vector above)*)
```

```
MaskProb = Function[{mask, Nloci},
  For[prob = 1; z = 1, z < Nloci, z++,
  If[BitGet[mask, z] == BitGet[mask, z - 1],
  prob *= (1 - recreate[z]),
  prob *= recreate[z]]];
```

```
(*generates the two zygote genotypes (zyg1 and zyg2)
  from two parental genotypes (i and j) for a given mask.*)
```

```

ZygoteGenotypes = Function[{i, j, mask},
  For[zyg1 = 0; zyg2 = 0; k = 0, k < Nloci, k++,
    If[BitGet[mask, k] == 0,
      zyg1 = BitOr[zyg1, (BitAnd[i, (2^k)])];
      zyg2 = BitOr[zyg2, (BitAnd[j, (2^k)])],
      zyg1 = BitOr[zyg1, (BitAnd[j, (2^k)])];
      zyg2 = BitOr[zyg2, (BitAnd[i, (2^k)])]]];

(*Produce a 3-dimensional matrix with the cells representing
the probability of producing a zygote genotype (k) from parental
genotypes i (mother) and j (father). Multiplying this matrix with
the mating table that gives the proportions of different male-
female genotype mating combinations will give the
frequency of zygote genotypes in the new generation
(after summing across parental genotypes).*)

RecTable = Table[0, {i, Geno}, {j, Geno}, {k, Geno}];
For[i = 0, i < Geno, i++,
  For[j = 0, j < Geno, j++,
    For[mask = 0, mask < masklim, mask++,
      MaskProb[mask, Nloci];
      zygoteProb = (1/2) * prob;
      ZygoteGenotypes[i, j, mask];
      RecTable[[i + 1], [j + 1], [zyg1 + 1]] += zygoteProb;
      RecTable[[i + 1], [j + 1], [zyg2 + 1]] += zygoteProb;]]]

(*uncomment this line to view the recombination table*)
(*MatrixForm[RecTable]*)

(*make a vector that will perform Natural Selection on males,
affecting gene frequencies before mating.*)

msel = Table[i, {i, 1, 8}];
u = Total[genotypes[[{1, 5}]]] + (1 - st) * Total[genotypes[[{2, 6}]]] +
  (1 - sb) * Total[genotypes[[{3, 7}]]] + (1 - sb) * (1 - st) * Total[genotypes[[{4, 8}]]];
msel[[{1, 5}]] = Table[genotypes[[i]] / u, {i, {1, 5}}];
msel[[{2, 6}]] = Table[((1 - st) * genotypes[[i]]) / u, {i, {2, 6}}];
msel[[{3, 7}]] = Table[((1 - sb) * genotypes[[i]]) / u, {i, {3, 7}}];
msel[[{4, 8}]] = Table[((1 - sb) * (1 - st) * genotypes[[i]]) / u, {i, {4, 8}}];

zb = Total[msel[[{1, 2, 5, 6}]]] + (ab + 1) * Total[msel[[{3, 4, 7, 8}]]];

z1 = Total[msel[[{1, 5}]]] * (c + (1 - c) * (1 / (at + 2))) +
  Total[msel[[{2, 6}]]] * (c + (1 - c) * ((at + 1) / (at + 2))) +
  Total[msel[[{3, 7}]]] * (c * (1 -  $\gamma$ ) + (1 - c * (1 -  $\gamma$ )) * (1 / (at + 2))) +
  Total[msel[[{4, 8}]]] * (c * (1 -  $\gamma$ ) + (1 - c * (1 -  $\gamma$ )) * ((at + 1) / (at + 2)));

```

```

z2 = (Total[mse1[{1, 5}]] / zb) * (c + (1 - c) * (1 / (at + 2))) +
      (Total[mse1[{2, 6}]] / zb) * (c + (1 - c) * ((at + 1) / (at + 2))) +
      Total[mse1[{3, 7}]] * ((1 + ab) / zb) * (c * (1 - γ) + (1 - c * (1 - γ)) * (1 / (at + 2))) +
      Total[mse1[{4, 8}]] * ((1 + ab) / zb) *
      (c * (1 - γ) + (1 - c * (1 - γ)) * ((at + 1) / (at + 2)));

```

```

(*Selection on females resulting from
cost of the female bower preference, R2*)

```

```

fse1 = Table[i, {i, 1, 8}];
v = Total[genotypes[1 ;; 4]] + (1 - sr) * Total[genotypes[5 ;; 8]];
fse1[1 ;; 4] = Table[genotypes[i] / v, {i, 1, 4}];
fse1[5 ;; 8] = Table[((1 - sr) * genotypes[i]) / v, {i, 5, 8}];

```

```

(*mating probability matrix-what proportion of matings
will be from each pairing strictly based on genotype frequency,
female choice, coercion, and bower type.*)
(*note that the mating matrix in the code here is
the transpose of the arrangement presented in Table 2,
with female genotypes as the "rows" and male genotypes as the "columns."
This is purely organizational; they are exactly equivalent*)

```

```

Mating = Table[Table[i, {i, 1, 8}], {j, 1, 8}];

```

```

(*for mating with R1 females*)

```

```

(*T1B1 males*)

```

```

Mating[1 ;; 4, {1, 5}] =
Table[Table[ $\frac{fse1[j] \left( mse1[i] \left( c + \frac{1-c}{at+2} \right) \right)}{z1}$ , {i, {1, 5}}], {j, 1, 4}];

```

```

(*T2B1 males*)

```

```

Mating[1 ;; 4, {2, 6}] =
Table[Table[ $\frac{fse1[j] \left( mse1[i] \left( c + \frac{(1-c)(at+1)}{at+2} \right) \right)}{z1}$ , {i, {2, 6}}], {j, 1, 4}];

```

```

(*T1B2 males*)

```

```

Mating[1 ;; 4, {3, 7}] =
Table[Table[ $\frac{fse1[j] \left( mse1[i] \left( c(1-\gamma) + \frac{1-c(1-\gamma)}{at+2} \right) \right)}{z1}$ , {i, {3, 7}}], {j, 1, 4}];

```

```

(*T2B2 males*)

```

```

Mating[1 ;; 4, {4, 8}] = Table[
Table[ $\frac{fse1[j] \left( mse1[i] \left( c(1-\gamma) + \frac{(1-c(1-\gamma))(at+1)}{at+2} \right) \right)}{z1}$ , {i, {4, 8}}], {j, 1, 4}];

```

(*for mating with R2 females*)

(*T1B1 males*)

Mating[[5 ;; 8, {1, 5}]] =
 Table[Table[$\frac{\text{fsel}[[j]] \left(\text{msel}[[i]] \left(c + \frac{1-c}{at+2} \right) \right)}{z_b z_2}$, {i, {1, 5}}], {j, 5, 8}];

(*T2B1 males*)

Mating[[5 ;; 8, {2, 6}]] =
 Table[Table[$\frac{\text{fsel}[[j]] \left(\text{msel}[[i]] \left(c + \frac{(1-c)(at+1)}{at+2} \right) \right)}{z_b z_2}$, {i, {2, 6}}], {j, 5, 8}];

(*T1B2 males*)

Mating[[5 ;; 8, {3, 7}]] = Table[
 Table[$\frac{\text{fsel}[[j]] \left(\text{msel}[[i]] (1 + ab) \left(c (1 - \gamma) + \frac{1-c(1-\gamma)}{at+2} \right) \right)}{z_b z_2}$, {i, {3, 7}}], {j, 5, 8}];

(*T2B2 males*)

Mating[[5 ;; 8, {4, 8}]] = Table[Table[
 $\frac{\text{fsel}[[j]] \left(\text{msel}[[i]] (1 + ab) \left(c (1 - \gamma) + \frac{(1-c(1-\gamma))(at+1)}{at+2} \right) \right)}{z_b z_2}$, {i, {4, 8}}], {j, 5, 8}];

(*Multiply the mating table by the recombination matrix to get the contributions to each zygote genotype weighted by the proportions of each mate pairing*)

materec = RecTable * Mating;

(*sum across each element of each 8-tuple for the mate pairings across the new matrix to get the final genotype frequencies.*)

genotypes[[1 ;; 8]] =
 Table[Simplify[Total[Flatten[materec[[1 ;; 8, 1 ;; 8, i]]]], {i, 1, 8}];

(*once genotypes are assigned, some frequency from T2 alleles are shifted over to T1 alleles due to biased mutation*)

mgenotypes = {1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8};
 mgenotypes[[{2, 4, 6, 8}]] = (1 - m) * genotypes[[{2, 4, 6, 8}]];
 mgenotypes[[{1, 3, 5, 7}]] = m * genotypes[[{2, 4, 6, 8}]] + genotypes[[{1, 3, 5, 7}]];

T21 = Total[mgenotypes[[{2, 4, 6, 8}]]];

B21 = Total[mgenotypes[[{3, 4, 7, 8}]]];

R21 = Total[mgenotypes[[5 ;; 8]]];

```
DTB1 = Total[mgenotypes[{4, 8}]] - T21 * B21;
DTR1 = Total[mgenotypes[{6, 8}]] - T21 * R21;
DBR1 = Total[mgenotypes[{7, 8}]] - B21 * R21;
DTBR1 = mgenotypes[8] - T21 * DBR1 - B21 * DTR1 - R21 * DTB1 - T21 * B21 * R21;
```

```
In[ ]:= (*get the recursions*)
```

```
ΔT2 = T21 - T2;
ΔB2 = B21 - B2;
ΔR2 = R21 - R2;
ΔDTB = DTB1 - DTB;
ΔDTR = DTR1 - DTR;
ΔDBR = DBR1 - DBR;
ΔDTBR = DTBR1 - DTBR;
```

2. Get first-order approximations for the recursions for the allele frequencies

We can approximate the expressions by assuming that the viability costs to the various traits as well as the strength of female preference, male coercion, and mutation are weak. We left the magnitude of γ (the protectiveness of the remodeling trait) unconstrained. We can express those parameters as coefficients of a very small number ζ .

```
In[ ]:= st = ζ * stapprox;
sb = ζ * sbapprox;
sr = ζ * srapprox;
at = ζ * atapprox;
ab = ζ * abapprox;
c = ζ * capprox;
m = ζ * mapprox;
```

Get the allele frequency recursions to the first order

```
In[ ]:= ΔT2approx = Simplify[Normal[Series[ΔT2, {ζ, 0, 1}]]]
ΔB2approx = Simplify[Normal[Series[ΔB2, {ζ, 0, 1}]]]
ΔR2approx = Simplify[Normal[Series[ΔR2, {ζ, 0, 1}]]]
```

```
Out[ ]:=  $\frac{1}{2} \left( abapprox DTB R2 - DTR srapprox + atapprox T2 - 2 mapprox T2 - \right. \\ \left. stapprox T2 - atapprox T2^2 + stapprox T2^2 - DTB (sbapprox + capprox \gamma) \right) \zeta$ 
```

$$\text{Out[*]} := \frac{1}{2} \left(\text{atapprox DTB} - \text{abapprox} (-1 + B2) B2 R2 - B2 \text{sbapprox} + \right. \\ \left. B2^2 \text{sbapprox} - \text{DBR srapprox} - \text{DTB stapprox} - B2 \text{capprox} \gamma + B2^2 \text{capprox} \gamma \right) \xi$$

$$\text{Out[*]} := \frac{1}{2} \left(\text{atapprox DTR} + \text{abapprox DBR R2} - \text{DBR sbapprox} - \right. \\ \left. R2 \text{srapprox} + R2^2 \text{srapprox} - \text{DTR stapprox} - \text{capprox DBR} \gamma \right) \xi$$

clean up notation

`In[*]:= Clear[at, ab, sr, c, st, sb, m]`

`Simplify[{\Delta T2approx, \Delta B2approx, \Delta R2approx}] /. {atapprox \to at, abapprox \to ab, srapprox \to sr, capprox \to c, stapprox \to st, sbapprox \to sb, mapprox \to m, \xi \to 1}`

$$\left\{ \frac{1}{2} \left(\text{ab DTB R2} - \text{DTR sr} + \text{at T2} - 2 m T2 - \text{st T2} - \text{at T2}^2 + \text{st T2}^2 - \text{DTB} (\text{sb} + c \gamma) \right), \right. \\ \frac{1}{2} \left(\text{at DTB} - \text{ab} (-1 + B2) B2 R2 - B2 \text{sb} + B2^2 \text{sb} - \text{DBR sr} - \text{DTB st} - B2 c \gamma + B2^2 c \gamma \right), \\ \left. \frac{1}{2} \left(\text{at DTR} + \text{ab DBR R2} - \text{DBR sb} - R2 \text{sr} + R2^2 \text{sr} - \text{DTR st} - c \text{DBR} \gamma \right) \right\}$$

(*check simplifications for typesetting*)

$$\text{In[*]:= Simplify}\left[\left(1/2\right)\left(\left(\text{at} - \text{st}\right)\left(1 - T2\right)T2 + \text{DTB}\left(\text{ab} * R2 - \left(\text{sb} + c * \gamma\right)\right) - \text{DTR} * \text{sr} - 2 m * T2\right) == \right. \\ \left. \frac{1}{2} \left(\text{ab DTB R2} - \text{DTR sr} + \text{at T2} - 2 m T2 - \text{st T2} - \text{at T2}^2 + \text{st T2}^2 - \text{DTB} (\text{sb} + c \gamma) \right) \right]$$

`Out[*]:= True`

$$\frac{1}{2} \left(\text{DTB} (\text{ab R2} - (c \gamma + \text{sb})) + (1 - T2) T2 (\text{at} - \text{st}) - \text{DTR sr} - 2 m T2 \right)$$

$$\text{In[*]:= Simplify}\left[\left(1/2\right)\left(\left(\text{ab} * R2 - \left(\text{sb} + c * \gamma\right)\right)\left(1 - B2\right)B2 + \text{DTB}\left(\text{at} - \text{st}\right) - \text{DBR} * \text{sr}\right) == \right. \\ \left. \frac{1}{2} \left(\text{at DTB} - \text{ab} (-1 + B2) B2 R2 - B2 \text{sb} + B2^2 \text{sb} - \text{DBR sr} - \text{DTB st} - B2 c \gamma + B2^2 c \gamma \right) \right]$$

`Out[*]:= True`

$$\frac{1}{2} \left((1 - B2) B2 (\text{ab R2} - (c \gamma + \text{sb})) + \text{DTB} (\text{at} - \text{st}) - \text{DBR sr} \right)$$

$$\text{In[*]:= Simplify}\left[\left(1/2\right)\left(\text{DBR}\left(\text{ab} * R2 - \left(\text{sb} + c * \gamma\right)\right) + \text{DTR}\left(\text{at} - \text{st}\right) - \text{sr}\left(1 - R2\right)R2\right) == \right. \\ \left. \frac{1}{2} \left(\text{at DTR} + \text{ab DBR R2} - \text{DBR sb} - R2 \text{sr} + R2^2 \text{sr} - \text{DTR st} - c \text{DBR} \gamma \right) \right]$$

`Out[*]:= True`

$$\frac{1}{2} \left(\text{DBR} (\text{ab R2} - (c \gamma + \text{sb})) + \text{DTR} (\text{at} - \text{st}) - ((1 - R2) R2 \text{sr}) \right)$$

3. Get approximate solutions for the linkages assuming

weak selection and Quasi-Linkage Equilibrium

Make functions for the recursions of the D 's in terms of a polynomial in a single variable. These will be series of coefficients of a very small number ζ

```
In[ ]:= fΔDTB = ΔDTB /. {DTB → DTBA0 + DTBA1 * ζ + DTBA2 * ζ^2 + DTBA3 * ζ^3 + DTBA4 * ζ^4,
  DTR → DTRA0 + DTRA1 * ζ + DTRA2 * ζ^2 + DTRA3 * ζ^3 + DTRA4 * ζ^4,
  DBR → DBRA0 + DBRA1 * ζ + DBRA2 * ζ^2 + DBRA3 * ζ^3 + DBRA4 * ζ^4,
  DTBR → DTBRA0 + DTBRA1 * ζ + DTBRA2 * ζ^2 + DTBRA3 * ζ^3 + DTBRA4 * ζ^4};
```

```
fΔDTR = ΔDTR /. {DTB → DTBA0 + DTBA1 * ζ + DTBA2 * ζ^2 + DTBA3 * ζ^3 + DTBA4 * ζ^4,
  DTR → DTRA0 + DTRA1 * ζ + DTRA2 * ζ^2 + DTRA3 * ζ^3 + DTRA4 * ζ^4,
  DBR → DBRA0 + DBRA1 * ζ + DBRA2 * ζ^2 + DBRA3 * ζ^3 + DBRA4 * ζ^4,
  DTBR → DTBRA0 + DTBRA1 * ζ + DTBRA2 * ζ^2 + DTBRA3 * ζ^3 + DTBRA4 * ζ^4};
```

```
fΔDBR = ΔDBR /. {DTB → DTBA0 + DTBA1 * ζ + DTBA2 * ζ^2 + DTBA3 * ζ^3 + DTBA4 * ζ^4,
  DTR → DTRA0 + DTRA1 * ζ + DTRA2 * ζ^2 + DTRA3 * ζ^3 + DTRA4 * ζ^4,
  DBR → DBRA0 + DBRA1 * ζ + DBRA2 * ζ^2 + DBRA3 * ζ^3 + DBRA4 * ζ^4,
  DTBR → DTBRA0 + DTBRA1 * ζ + DTBRA2 * ζ^2 + DTBRA3 * ζ^3 + DTBRA4 * ζ^4};
```

```
fΔDTBR = ΔDTBR /. {DTB → DTBA0 + DTBA1 * ζ + DTBA2 * ζ^2 + DTBA3 * ζ^3 + DTBA4 * ζ^4,
  DTR → DTRA0 + DTRA1 * ζ + DTRA2 * ζ^2 + DTRA3 * ζ^3 + DTRA4 * ζ^4,
  DBR → DBRA0 + DBRA1 * ζ + DBRA2 * ζ^2 + DBRA3 * ζ^3 + DBRA4 * ζ^4,
  DTBR → DTBRA0 + DTBRA1 * ζ + DTBRA2 * ζ^2 + DTBRA3 * ζ^3 + DTBRA4 * ζ^4};
```

again, assume weak selection but leave γ large

```
st = ζ * stapprox;
sb = ζ * sbapprox;
sr = ζ * srapprox;
at = ζ * atapprox;
ab = ζ * abapprox;
c = ζ * capprox;
m = ζ * mapprox;
```

Get the first (zero-th order) term for each recursion expression

```
In[ ]:= DTBA0eq = Normal[Simplify[Series[fΔDTB, {ζ, 0, 0}]]]
```

```
Out[ ]:= -  $\frac{DTBA0}{2}$ 
```

```
In[ ]:= DTRA0eq = Normal[Simplify[Series[fΔDTR, {ζ, 0, 0}]]]
```

```
Out[ ]:= -  $\frac{DTRA0}{2}$ 
```

```
In[ ]:= DBRA0eq = Normal[Simplify[Series[fΔDBR, {ζ, 0, 0}]]]
```

$$\text{Out}[*]:= -\frac{\text{DBRA0}}{2}$$

`In[*]:= DTBRA0eq = Normal[Simplify[Series[fΔDTBR, {ξ, 0, 0}]]]`

$$\text{Out}[*]:= -\frac{3 \text{DTBRA0}}{4}$$

`In[*]:= Simplify[Solve[{DTBA0eq == 0, DTRA0eq == 0, DBRA0eq == 0, DTBRA0eq == 0}, {DTBA0, DTRA0, DBRA0, DTBRA0}]]`

`{{DTBA0 → 0, DTRA0 → 0, DBRA0 → 0, DTBRA0 → 0}}`

(*all the zeroth order terms are zero!*)

Get the second (first-order) terms

`In[*]:= DTBA1eq = Normal[Simplify[Series[fΔDTB, {ξ, 0, 1}]]]`

$$\text{Out}[*]:= -\frac{\text{DTBA0}}{2} + \frac{1}{4} \left(-2 \text{DTBA1} - 2 \text{DTBA0 mapprox} + \right. \\ \left. \text{abapprox} \left(\text{DBRA0 DTBA0} + \text{B2 DTRA0} - \text{B2}^2 \text{DTRA0} + \text{DTBA0 R2} - 2 \text{B2 DTBA0 R2} \right) - \right. \\ \left. \text{DTBA0 sbapprox} + 2 \text{B2 DTBA0 sbapprox} - \text{DTBRA0 srapprox} - \right. \\ \left. \text{DTBA0 stapprox} + 2 \text{DTBA0 stapprox T2} + \text{atapprox} \left(\text{DTBA0} - 2 \text{DTBA0 T2} \right) - \right. \\ \left. \text{capprox DTBA0 } \gamma + 2 \text{B2 capprox DTBA0 } \gamma \right) \xi$$

`In[*]:= DTRA1eq = Normal[Simplify[Series[fΔDTR, {ξ, 0, 1}]]]`

$$\text{Out}[*]:= -\frac{\text{DTRA0}}{2} + \frac{1}{4} \left(\text{abapprox DBRA0 DTRA0} - 2 \text{DTRA1} - \right. \\ \left. 2 \text{DTRA0 mapprox} + \text{abapprox R2} \left(\text{DTBA0} + \text{DTBRA0} - \text{DTBA0 R2} \right) - \right. \\ \left. \text{DTBRA0 sbapprox} - \text{DTRA0 srapprox} + 2 \text{DTRA0 R2 srapprox} - \text{DTRA0 stapprox} + \right. \\ \left. 2 \text{DTRA0 stapprox T2} + \text{atapprox} \left(\text{DTRA0} - 2 \text{DTRA0 T2} \right) - \text{capprox DTBRA0 } \gamma \right) \xi$$

`In[*]:= DBRA1eq = Normal[Simplify[Series[fΔDBR, {ξ, 0, 1}]]]`

$$\text{Out}[*]:= -\frac{\text{DBRA0}}{2} + \frac{1}{4} \left(-2 \text{DBRA1} + \text{atapprox DTBRA0} + \right. \\ \left. \text{abapprox} \left(\text{DBRA0}^2 + (-1 + \text{B2}) \text{B2} (-1 + \text{R2}) \text{R2} + \text{DBRA0} (\text{R2} - 2 \text{B2 R2}) \right) - \right. \\ \left. \text{DBRA0 sbapprox} + 2 \text{B2 DBRA0 sbapprox} - \text{DBRA0 srapprox} + 2 \text{DBRA0 R2 srapprox} - \right. \\ \left. \text{DTBRA0 stapprox} - \text{capprox DBRA0 } \gamma + 2 \text{B2 capprox DBRA0 } \gamma \right) \xi$$

`In[*]:= DTBRA1eq = Normal[Simplify[Series[fΔDTBR, {ξ, 0, 1}]]]`

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{Out}[\ast] := & -\frac{3 \text{DTBRA0}}{4} + \\
& \frac{1}{8} \left(-6 \text{DTBRA1} - 2 \text{DTBRA0} \text{mapprox} + \text{abapprox} \left(\text{B2}^2 \text{DTRA0} (-1 + 2 \text{R2}) + \text{DBRA0} (\text{DTBA0} + \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 2 \text{DTBRA0} + \text{DTRA0} - 2 \text{B2} \text{DTRA0} - 4 \text{DTBA0} \text{R2}) + \text{R2} (\text{DTBA0} + \text{DTBRA0} - \text{DTBA0} \text{R2}) + \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \text{B2} (\text{DTRA0} - 2 \text{DTRA0} \text{R2} - 2 \text{R2} (\text{DTBA0} + \text{DTBRA0} - \text{DTBA0} \text{R2})) \right) \right) + \\
& 2 \text{DBRA0} \text{DTBA0} \text{sbapprox} - \text{DTBRA0} \text{sbapprox} + 2 \text{B2} \text{DTBRA0} \text{sbapprox} - \\
& \text{DTBRA0} \text{srapprox} + 2 \text{DBRA0} \text{DTRA0} \text{srapprox} + 2 \text{DTBRA0} \text{R2} \text{srapprox} - \\
& \text{DTBRA0} \text{stapprox} + 2 \text{DTBA0} \text{DTRA0} \text{stapprox} + 2 \text{DTBRA0} \text{stapprox} \text{T2} + \\
& \text{atapprox} (\text{DTBRA0} - 2 \text{DTBA0} \text{DTRA0} - 2 \text{DTBRA0} \text{T2}) + \\
& 2 \text{capprox} \text{DBRA0} \text{DTBA0} \gamma - \text{capprox} \text{DTBRA0} \gamma + 2 \text{B2} \text{capprox} \text{DTBRA0} \gamma) \zeta
\end{aligned}$$

Plug in solutions for 0 th order

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{In}[\ast] := & \text{DTBA1eq} = \text{Simplify}[\text{DTBA1eq} /. \{\text{DTBA0} \rightarrow 0, \text{DTRA0} \rightarrow 0, \text{DBRA0} \rightarrow 0, \text{DTBRA0} \rightarrow 0\}] \\
\text{Out}[\ast] := & -\frac{\text{DTBA1} \zeta}{2}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{In}[\ast] := & \text{DTRA1eq} = \text{Simplify}[\text{DTRA1eq} /. \{\text{DTBA0} \rightarrow 0, \text{DTRA0} \rightarrow 0, \text{DBRA0} \rightarrow 0, \text{DTBRA0} \rightarrow 0\}] \\
\text{Out}[\ast] := & -\frac{\text{DTRA1} \zeta}{2}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{In}[\ast] := & \text{DBRA1eq} = \text{Simplify}[\text{DBRA1eq} /. \{\text{DTBA0} \rightarrow 0, \text{DTRA0} \rightarrow 0, \text{DBRA0} \rightarrow 0, \text{DTBRA0} \rightarrow 0\}] \\
\text{Out}[\ast] := & \frac{1}{4} (-2 \text{DBRA1} + \text{abapprox} (-1 + \text{B2}) \text{B2} (-1 + \text{R2}) \text{R2}) \zeta
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{In}[\ast] := & \text{DTBRA1eq} = \text{Simplify}[\text{DTBRA1eq} /. \{\text{DTBA0} \rightarrow 0, \text{DTRA0} \rightarrow 0, \text{DBRA0} \rightarrow 0, \text{DTBRA0} \rightarrow 0\}] \\
\text{Out}[\ast] := & -\frac{3 \text{DTBRA1} \zeta}{4}
\end{aligned}$$

Solve for 1 st order terms

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{In}[\ast] := & \text{Simplify}[\text{Solve}[\{\text{DTBA1eq} == 0, \text{DTRA1eq} == 0, \text{DBRA1eq} == 0, \text{DTBRA1eq} == 0\}, \\
& \{\text{DTBA1}, \text{DTRA1}, \text{DBRA1}, \text{DTBRA1}\}]] \\
& \left\{ \left\{ \text{DTBA1} \rightarrow 0, \text{DTRA1} \rightarrow 0, \text{DBRA1} \rightarrow \frac{1}{2} \text{abapprox} (-1 + \text{B2}) \text{B2} (-1 + \text{R2}) \text{R2}, \text{DTBRA1} \rightarrow 0 \right\} \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

(*the only first-order term is fisherian sexual selection on the bower trait*)

(*need to keep going to uncover the dynamimcs of interest*)

Get the third (second – order) terms

$$\text{In}[\ast] := \text{DTBA2eq} = \text{Normal}[\text{Simplify}[\text{Series}[\text{f}\Delta\text{DTB}, \{\zeta, 0, 2\}]]];$$

$$\text{DTRA2eq} = \text{Normal}[\text{Simplify}[\text{Series}[\text{f}\Delta\text{DTR}, \{\zeta, 0, 2\}]]];$$

$$\text{DBRA2eq} = \text{Normal}[\text{Simplify}[\text{Series}[\text{f}\Delta\text{DBR}, \{\zeta, 0, 2\}]]];$$

$$\text{DTBRA2eq} = \text{Normal}[\text{Simplify}[\text{Series}[\text{f}\Delta\text{DTBR}, \{\zeta, 0, 2\}]]];$$

Plug in solutions for 0 th and first order

$$\text{In[*]:= DTBA2eq = Simplify}\left[\text{DTBA2eq} /. \left\{\text{DTBA0} \rightarrow 0, \text{DTRA0} \rightarrow 0, \text{DBRA0} \rightarrow 0, \text{DTBRA0} \rightarrow 0, \text{DTBA1} \rightarrow 0, \right.\right.$$

$$\left.\left.\text{DTRA1} \rightarrow 0, \text{DBRA1} \rightarrow \frac{1}{2} \text{ abapprox } (-1 + \text{B2}) \text{ B2 } (-1 + \text{R2}) \text{ R2}, \text{DTBRA1} \rightarrow 0\right\}\right]$$

$$\text{Out[*]:= } -\frac{1}{2} (\text{DTBA2} + \text{atapprox} \text{ B2} \text{ capprox} \text{ T2} (-1 + \text{B2} + \text{T2} - \text{B2} \text{ T2}) \gamma) \zeta^2$$

$$\text{In[*]:= DTRA2eq = Simplify}\left[\text{DTRA2eq} /. \left\{\text{DTBA0} \rightarrow 0, \text{DTRA0} \rightarrow 0, \text{DBRA0} \rightarrow 0, \text{DTBRA0} \rightarrow 0, \text{DTBA1} \rightarrow 0, \right.\right.$$

$$\left.\left.\text{DTRA1} \rightarrow 0, \text{DBRA1} \rightarrow \frac{1}{2} \text{ abapprox } (-1 + \text{B2}) \text{ B2 } (-1 + \text{R2}) \text{ R2}, \text{DTBRA1} \rightarrow 0\right\}\right]$$

$$\text{Out[*]:= } -\frac{\text{DTRA2} \zeta^2}{2}$$

$$\text{In[*]:= DBRA2eq = Simplify}\left[\text{DBRA2eq} /. \left\{\text{DTBA0} \rightarrow 0, \text{DTRA0} \rightarrow 0, \text{DBRA0} \rightarrow 0, \text{DTBRA0} \rightarrow 0, \text{DTBA1} \rightarrow 0, \right.\right.$$

$$\left.\left.\text{DTRA1} \rightarrow 0, \text{DBRA1} \rightarrow \frac{1}{2} \text{ abapprox } (-1 + \text{B2}) \text{ B2 } (-1 + \text{R2}) \text{ R2}, \text{DTBRA1} \rightarrow 0\right\}\right]$$

$$\text{Out[*]:= } -\frac{1}{8} (4 \text{ DBRA2} + \text{abapprox} (-1 + \text{B2}) \text{ B2} (-1 + \text{R2}) \text{ R2} (-\text{abapprox} \text{ R2} + 2 \text{ abapprox} \text{ B2} (1 + \text{R2}) +$$

$$3 (\text{sbapprox} - 2 \text{ B2} \text{ sbapprox} + \text{srapprox} - 2 \text{ R2} \text{ srapprox} + (1 - 2 \text{ B2}) \text{ capprox} \gamma)) \zeta^2$$

$$\text{In[*]:= DTBRA2eq =}$$

$$\text{Simplify}\left[\text{DTBRA2eq} /. \left\{\text{DTBA0} \rightarrow 0, \text{DTRA0} \rightarrow 0, \text{DBRA0} \rightarrow 0, \text{DTBRA0} \rightarrow 0, \text{DTBA1} \rightarrow 0, \right.\right.$$

$$\left.\left.\text{DTRA1} \rightarrow 0, \text{DBRA1} \rightarrow \frac{1}{2} \text{ abapprox } (-1 + \text{B2}) \text{ B2 } (-1 + \text{R2}) \text{ R2}, \text{DTBRA1} \rightarrow 0\right\}\right]$$

$$\text{Out[*]:= } -\frac{3 \text{ DTBRA2} \zeta^2}{4}$$

Solve for second-order terms

$$\text{In[*]:= Simplify}\left[\text{Solve}\left[\left\{\text{DTBA2eq} == 0, \text{DTRA2eq} == 0, \text{DBRA2eq} == 0, \text{DTBRA2eq} == 0\right\}, \left\{\text{DTBA2}, \text{DTRA2}, \text{DBRA2}, \text{DTBRA2}\right\}\right]\right]$$

$$\left\{\left\{\text{DTBA2} \rightarrow \text{atapprox} (-1 + \text{B2}) \text{ B2} \text{ capprox} (-1 + \text{T2}) \text{ T2} \gamma, \right.\right.$$

$$\left.\left.\text{DTRA2} \rightarrow 0, \text{DBRA2} \rightarrow -\frac{1}{4} \text{ abapprox} (-1 + \text{B2}) \text{ B2} (-1 + \text{R2}) \text{ R2} \right.\right.$$

$$\left.\left.(-\text{abapprox} \text{ R2} + 2 \text{ abapprox} \text{ B2} (1 + \text{R2}) + 3 (\text{sbapprox} - 2 \text{ B2} \text{ sbapprox} + \right.\right.$$

$$\left.\left.\text{srapprox} - 2 \text{ R2} \text{ srapprox} + (1 - 2 \text{ B2}) \text{ capprox} \gamma)\right), \text{DTBRA2} \rightarrow 0\right\}$$

Get the fourth (third-order) terms

$$\text{In[*]:= DTBA3eq = Normal}\left[\text{Simplify}\left[\text{Series}\left[\text{f}\Delta\text{DTB}, \{\zeta, 0, 3\}\right]\right]\right];$$

$$\text{DTRA3eq = Normal}\left[\text{Simplify}\left[\text{Series}\left[\text{f}\Delta\text{DTR}, \{\zeta, 0, 3\}\right]\right]\right];$$

$$\text{DBRA3eq = Normal}\left[\text{Simplify}\left[\text{Series}\left[\text{f}\Delta\text{DBR}, \{\zeta, 0, 3\}\right]\right]\right];$$

```
In[ ]:= DTBRA3eq = Normal[Simplify[Series[fΔDTBR, {ξ, 0, 3}]]];
```

Plug in solutions for the 0 th, first and second order

```
In[ ]:= DTBA3eq = Simplify[DTBA3eq /. {DTBA0 → 0, DTRA0 → 0, DBRA0 → 0, DTBRA0 → 0,
DTBA1 → 0, DTRA1 → 0, DBRA1 →  $\frac{1}{2}$  abapprox (-1 + B2) B2 (-1 + R2) R2,
DTBRA1 → 0, DTBA2 → atapprox (-1 + B2) B2 capprox (-1 + T2) T2 γ,
DTRA2 → 0, DBRA2 →  $-\frac{1}{4}$  abapprox (-1 + B2) B2 (-1 + R2) R2
(- abapprox R2 + 2 abapprox B2 (1 + R2) + 3 (sbapprox - 2 B2 sbapprox +
srapprox - 2 R2 srapprox + (1 - 2 B2) capprox γ)), DTBRA2 → 0}];
```

```
DTRA3eq = Simplify[DTRA3eq /. {DTBA0 → 0, DTRA0 → 0, DBRA0 → 0, DTBRA0 → 0,
DTBA1 → 0, DTRA1 → 0, DBRA1 →  $\frac{1}{2}$  abapprox (-1 + B2) B2 (-1 + R2) R2,
DTBRA1 → 0, DTBA2 → atapprox (-1 + B2) B2 capprox (-1 + T2) T2 γ,
DTRA2 → 0, DBRA2 →  $-\frac{1}{4}$  abapprox (-1 + B2) B2 (-1 + R2) R2
(- abapprox R2 + 2 abapprox B2 (1 + R2) + 3 (sbapprox - 2 B2 sbapprox +
srapprox - 2 R2 srapprox + (1 - 2 B2) capprox γ)), DTBRA2 → 0}];
```

```
DBRA3eq = Simplify[DBRA3eq /. {DTBA0 → 0, DTRA0 → 0, DBRA0 → 0, DTBRA0 → 0,
DTBA1 → 0, DTRA1 → 0, DBRA1 →  $\frac{1}{2}$  abapprox (-1 + B2) B2 (-1 + R2) R2,
DTBRA1 → 0, DTBA2 → atapprox (-1 + B2) B2 capprox (-1 + T2) T2 γ,
DTRA2 → 0, DBRA2 →  $-\frac{1}{4}$  abapprox (-1 + B2) B2 (-1 + R2) R2
(- abapprox R2 + 2 abapprox B2 (1 + R2) + 3 (sbapprox - 2 B2 sbapprox +
srapprox - 2 R2 srapprox + (1 - 2 B2) capprox γ)), DTBRA2 → 0}];
```

```
DTBRA3eq =
Simplify[DTBRA3eq /. {DTBA0 → 0, DTRA0 → 0, DBRA0 → 0, DTBRA0 → 0, DTBA1 → 0,
DTRA1 → 0, DBRA1 →  $\frac{1}{2}$  abapprox (-1 + B2) B2 (-1 + R2) R2, DTBRA1 → 0,
DTBA2 → atapprox (-1 + B2) B2 capprox (-1 + T2) T2 γ,
DTRA2 → 0, DBRA2 →  $-\frac{1}{4}$  abapprox (-1 + B2) B2 (-1 + R2) R2
(- abapprox R2 + 2 abapprox B2 (1 + R2) + 3 (sbapprox - 2 B2 sbapprox +
srapprox - 2 R2 srapprox + (1 - 2 B2) capprox γ)), DTBRA2 → 0}];
```

Solve for third-order terms

```
In[ ]:= Simplify[Solve[{DTBA3eq == 0, DTRA3eq == 0, DBRA3eq == 0, DTBRA3eq == 0},
{DTBA3, DTRA3, DBRA3, DTBRA3}]]
```

$$\left\{ \left\{ \begin{aligned} &DTBA3 \rightarrow -\frac{1}{2} \text{atapprox} (-1 + B2) B2 \text{capprox} (-1 + T2) T2 \gamma \\ &(4 \text{mapprox} - 3 \text{abapprox} R2 + 6 \text{abapprox} B2 R2 + 3 \text{sbapprox} - 6 B2 \text{sbapprox} + \\ &3 \text{stapprox} - 6 \text{stapprox} T2 + \text{atapprox} (-2 + 6 T2) + \text{capprox} (4 + \gamma - 6 B2 \gamma)), \\ &DTRA3 \rightarrow -2 \text{abapprox} \text{atapprox} (-1 + B2) B2 \text{capprox} (-1 + R2) R2 (-1 + T2) T2 \gamma, \\ &DBRA3 \rightarrow \frac{1}{8} \text{abapprox} (-1 + B2) B2 (-1 + R2) R2 \\ &(\text{abapprox}^2 (R2^2 - B2 R2 (3 + 7 R2) + B2^2 (4 + 7 R2 + 7 R2^2)) + \\ &3 (1 - 8 B2 + 10 B2^2) \text{sbapprox}^2 + 3 \text{srapprox}^2 - 24 R2 \text{srapprox}^2 + 30 R2^2 \text{srapprox}^2 - \\ &6 \text{atapprox} \text{capprox} \gamma + 12 \text{atapprox} B2 \text{capprox} \gamma + 6 \text{capprox}^2 \gamma - \\ &12 B2 \text{capprox}^2 \gamma + 10 \text{capprox} \text{srapprox} \gamma - 20 B2 \text{capprox} \text{srapprox} \gamma - \\ &20 \text{capprox} R2 \text{srapprox} \gamma + 40 B2 \text{capprox} R2 \text{srapprox} \gamma + 12 \text{atapprox} \text{capprox} T2 \gamma - \\ &24 \text{atapprox} B2 \text{capprox} T2 \gamma + 3 \text{capprox}^2 \gamma^2 - 24 B2 \text{capprox}^2 \gamma^2 + 30 B2^2 \text{capprox}^2 \gamma^2 + \\ &2 \text{sbapprox} (5 (-1 + 2 B2) (-1 + 2 R2) \text{srapprox} + 6 (1 - 5 B2 + 5 B2^2) \text{capprox} \gamma) - \\ &2 \text{abapprox} (2 B2^2 (4 + 7 R2) (\text{sbapprox} + \text{capprox} \gamma) + \\ &R2 (3 \text{sbapprox} + (3 - 5 R2) \text{srapprox} + 3 \text{capprox} \gamma) - \\ &B2 ((5 + 14 R2) \text{sbapprox} + (3 - 10 R2^2) \text{srapprox} + \text{capprox} (5 + 14 R2) \gamma))) , \\ &DTBRA3 \rightarrow \frac{2}{3} \text{abapprox} \text{atapprox} B2 (1 - 3 B2 + 2 B2^2) \text{capprox} (-1 + R2) R2 (-1 + T2) T2 \gamma \end{aligned} \right\} \right\}$$

Bring all the terms together and clean up notation

In[]:= Clear[at, ab, sr, c, st, sb, m, B2, R2, Teq, T2]

In[]:= DTBapprox = Simplify[atapprox (-1 + B2) B2 capprox (-1 + T2) T2 γ +

$$-\frac{1}{2} \text{atapprox} (-1 + B2) B2 \text{capprox} (-1 + T2) T2 \gamma$$

$$(4 \text{mapprox} - 3 \text{abapprox} R2 + 6 \text{abapprox} B2 R2 + 3 \text{sbapprox} - 6 B2 \text{sbapprox} + 3 \text{stapprox} - 6 \text{stapprox} T2 + \text{atapprox} (-2 + 6 T2) + \text{capprox} (4 + \gamma - 6 B2 \gamma)) / .$$

{atapprox → at, abapprox → ab, srapprox → sr, capprox → c, stapprox → st, sbapprox → sb, mapprox → m}]

$$\text{Out[]:= } -\frac{1}{2} \text{at} (-1 + B2) B2 \text{c} (-1 + T2) T2 \gamma (-2 + 4 \text{m} - 3 \text{ab} R2 +$$

$$6 \text{ab} B2 R2 + 3 \text{sb} - 6 B2 \text{sb} + 3 \text{st} - 6 \text{st} T2 + \text{at} (-2 + 6 T2) + \text{c} (4 + \gamma - 6 B2 \gamma))$$

$$-\frac{1}{2} \text{at} (-1 + B2) B2 \text{c} (-1 + T2) T2 \gamma (-2 + 4 \text{m} - 3 \text{ab} R2 +$$

$$6 \text{ab} B2 R2 + 3 \text{sb} - 6 B2 \text{sb} + 3 \text{st} - 6 \text{st} T2 + \text{at} (-2 + 6 T2) + \text{c} (4 + \gamma - 6 B2 \gamma))$$

In[]:= DTRapprox =

Simplify[-2 abapprox atapprox (-1 + B2) B2 capprox (-1 + R2) R2 (-1 + T2) T2 γ / .

{atapprox → at, abapprox → ab, srapprox → sr,

capprox → c, stapprox → st, sbapprox → sb, mapprox → m}]

$$\text{Out[]:= } -2 \text{ab} \text{at} (-1 + B2) B2 \text{c} (-1 + R2) R2 (-1 + T2) T2 \gamma$$

$$-2 \text{ab} \text{at} (-1 + B2) B2 \text{c} (-1 + R2) R2 (-1 + T2) T2 \gamma$$

In[*]:= DBRapprox =

$$\text{Simplify}\left[\frac{1}{2} \text{abapprox} (-1 + B2) B2 (-1 + R2) R2 + -\frac{1}{4} \text{abapprox} (-1 + B2) B2 (-1 + R2) R2 (-\text{abapprox} R2 + 2 \text{abapprox} B2 (1 + R2) + 3 (\text{sbapprox} - 2 B2 \text{sbapprox} + \text{srapprox} - 2 R2 \text{srapprox} + (1 - 2 B2) \text{capprox} \gamma)) + \frac{1}{8} \text{abapprox} (-1 + B2) B2 (-1 + R2) R2 (\text{abapprox}^2 (R2^2 - B2 R2 (3 + 7 R2) + B2^2 (4 + 7 R2 + 7 R2^2)) + 3 (1 - 8 B2 + 10 B2^2) \text{sbapprox}^2 + 3 \text{srapprox}^2 - 24 R2 \text{srapprox}^2 + 30 R2^2 \text{srapprox}^2 - 6 \text{atapprox} \text{capprox} \gamma + 12 \text{atapprox} B2 \text{capprox} \gamma + 6 \text{capprox}^2 \gamma - 12 B2 \text{capprox}^2 \gamma + 10 \text{capprox} \text{srapprox} \gamma - 20 B2 \text{capprox} \text{srapprox} \gamma - 20 \text{capprox} R2 \text{srapprox} \gamma + 40 B2 \text{capprox} R2 \text{srapprox} \gamma + 12 \text{atapprox} \text{capprox} T2 \gamma - 24 \text{atapprox} B2 \text{capprox} T2 \gamma + 3 \text{capprox}^2 \gamma^2 - 24 B2 \text{capprox}^2 \gamma^2 + 30 B2^2 \text{capprox}^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \text{sbapprox} (5 (-1 + 2 B2) (-1 + 2 R2) \text{srapprox} + 6 (1 - 5 B2 + 5 B2^2) \text{capprox} \gamma) - 2 \text{abapprox} (2 B2^2 (4 + 7 R2) (\text{sbapprox} + \text{capprox} \gamma) + R2 (3 \text{sbapprox} + (3 - 5 R2) \text{srapprox} + 3 \text{capprox} \gamma) - B2 ((5 + 14 R2) \text{sbapprox} + (3 - 10 R2^2) \text{srapprox} + \text{capprox} (5 + 14 R2) \gamma))\right] /. \{ \text{atapprox} \rightarrow \text{at}, \text{abapprox} \rightarrow \text{ab}, \text{srapprox} \rightarrow \text{sr}, \text{capprox} \rightarrow \text{c}, \text{stapprox} \rightarrow \text{st}, \text{sbapprox} \rightarrow \text{sb}, \text{mapprox} \rightarrow \text{m} \}$$

$$\text{Out[*]} = \frac{1}{8} \text{ab} (-1 + B2) B2 (-1 + R2) R2 (4 + 2 \text{ab} R2 - 4 \text{ab} B2 (1 + R2) + \text{ab}^2 (R2^2 - B2 R2 (3 + 7 R2) + B2^2 (4 + 7 R2 + 7 R2^2)) + 3 (1 - 8 B2 + 10 B2^2) \text{sb}^2 + 3 \text{sr}^2 - 24 R2 \text{sr}^2 + 30 R2^2 \text{sr}^2 - 6 \text{at} \text{c} \gamma + 12 \text{at} B2 \text{c} \gamma + 6 \text{c}^2 \gamma - 12 B2 \text{c}^2 \gamma + 10 \text{c} \text{sr} \gamma - 20 B2 \text{c} \text{sr} \gamma - 20 \text{c} R2 \text{sr} \gamma + 40 B2 \text{c} R2 \text{sr} \gamma + 12 \text{at} \text{c} T2 \gamma - 24 \text{at} B2 \text{c} T2 \gamma + 3 \text{c}^2 \gamma^2 - 24 B2 \text{c}^2 \gamma^2 + 30 B2^2 \text{c}^2 \gamma^2 - 6 (\text{sb} - 2 B2 \text{sb} + \text{sr} - 2 R2 \text{sr} + (1 - 2 B2) \text{c} \gamma) + 2 \text{sb} (5 (-1 + 2 B2) (-1 + 2 R2) \text{sr} + 6 (1 - 5 B2 + 5 B2^2) \text{c} \gamma) - 2 \text{ab} (2 B2^2 (4 + 7 R2) (\text{sb} + \text{c} \gamma) + R2 (3 \text{sb} + (3 - 5 R2) \text{sr} + 3 \text{c} \gamma) - B2 ((5 + 14 R2) \text{sb} + (3 - 10 R2^2) \text{sr} + \text{c} (5 + 14 R2) \gamma))$$

$$\frac{1}{8} \text{ab} (-1 + B2) B2 (-1 + R2) R2 (4 + 2 \text{ab} R2 - 4 \text{ab} B2 (1 + R2) + \text{ab}^2 (R2^2 - B2 R2 (3 + 7 R2) + B2^2 (4 + 7 R2 + 7 R2^2)) + 3 (1 - 8 B2 + 10 B2^2) \text{sb}^2 + 3 \text{sr}^2 - 24 R2 \text{sr}^2 + 30 R2^2 \text{sr}^2 - 6 \text{at} \text{c} \gamma + 12 \text{at} B2 \text{c} \gamma + 6 \text{c}^2 \gamma - 12 B2 \text{c}^2 \gamma + 10 \text{c} \text{sr} \gamma - 20 B2 \text{c} \text{sr} \gamma - 20 \text{c} R2 \text{sr} \gamma + 40 B2 \text{c} R2 \text{sr} \gamma + 12 \text{at} \text{c} T2 \gamma - 24 \text{at} B2 \text{c} T2 \gamma + 3 \text{c}^2 \gamma^2 - 24 B2 \text{c}^2 \gamma^2 + 30 B2^2 \text{c}^2 \gamma^2 - 6 (\text{sb} - 2 B2 \text{sb} + \text{sr} - 2 R2 \text{sr} + (1 - 2 B2) \text{c} \gamma) + 2 \text{sb} (5 (-1 + 2 B2) (-1 + 2 R2) \text{sr} + 6 (1 - 5 B2 + 5 B2^2) \text{c} \gamma) - 2 \text{ab} (2 B2^2 (4 + 7 R2) (\text{sb} + \text{c} \gamma) + R2 (3 \text{sb} + (3 - 5 R2) \text{sr} + 3 \text{c} \gamma) - B2 ((5 + 14 R2) \text{sb} + (3 - 10 R2^2) \text{sr} + \text{c} (5 + 14 R2) \gamma))$$

In[*]:= DTBRapprox =

$$\text{Simplify}\left[\frac{2}{3} \text{abapprox} \text{atapprox} B2 (1 - 3 B2 + 2 B2^2) \text{capprox} (-1 + R2) R2 (-1 + T2) T2 \gamma / . \{ \text{atapprox} \rightarrow \text{at}, \text{abapprox} \rightarrow \text{ab}, \text{srapprox} \rightarrow \text{sr}, \text{capprox} \rightarrow \text{c}, \text{stapprox} \rightarrow \text{st}, \text{sbapprox} \rightarrow \text{sb}, \text{mapprox} \rightarrow \text{m} \}\right]$$

$$\text{Out[*]} = \frac{2}{3} ab at B2 (1 - 3 B2 + 2 B2^2) c (-1 + R2) R2 (-1 + T2) T2 \gamma$$

$$\frac{2}{3} ab at B2 (1 - 3 B2 + 2 B2^2) c (-1 + R2) R2 (-1 + T2) T2 \gamma$$

(*check simplifications for typesetting*)

(*second-order coefficient for DBR*)

$$\text{Simplify} \left[-\frac{1}{4} ab \text{approx} (-1 + B2) B2 (-1 + R2) R2 (-ab \text{approx} R2 + 2 ab \text{approx} B2 (1 + R2) + 3 (sb \text{approx} - 2 B2 sb \text{approx} + sr \text{approx} - 2 R2 sr \text{approx} + (1 - 2 B2) c \text{approx} \gamma)) / . \{at \text{approx} \rightarrow at, ab \text{approx} \rightarrow ab, sr \text{approx} \rightarrow sr, c \text{approx} \rightarrow c, st \text{approx} \rightarrow st, sb \text{approx} \rightarrow sb, m \text{approx} \rightarrow m\} \right]$$

$$\text{Out[*]} = -\frac{1}{4} ab (-1 + B2) B2 (-1 + R2) R2 (-ab R2 + 2 ab B2 (1 + R2) + 3 (sb - 2 B2 sb + sr - 2 R2 sr + (1 - 2 B2) c \gamma))$$

$$\text{In[*]} := \text{Simplify} \left[-\frac{1}{4} ab (-1 + B2) B2 (-1 + R2) R2 (-ab R2 + 2 ab B2 (1 + R2) + 3 (sb - 2 B2 sb + sr - 2 R2 sr + (1 - 2 B2) c \gamma)) = \frac{1}{2} ab (-1 + B2) B2 (-1 + R2) R2 ((1/2) (ab (R2 - 2 B2 (1 + R2)) - 3 ((1 - 2 B2) (sb + c * \gamma) + sr (1 - 2 R2)))) \right]$$

Out[*] = True

$$\frac{1}{2} (ab (R2 - 2 B2 (R2 + 1)) - 3 ((1 - 2 B2) (c \gamma + sb) + (1 - 2 R2) sr))$$

(*pull out the third-order coefficient for DBR*)

$$\text{In[*]} := \text{Simplify} \left[\frac{1}{8} ab \text{approx} (-1 + B2) B2 (-1 + R2) R2 (ab \text{approx}^2 (R2^2 - B2 R2 (3 + 7 R2) + B2^2 (4 + 7 R2 + 7 R2^2)) + 3 (1 - 8 B2 + 10 B2^2) sb \text{approx}^2 + 3 sr \text{approx}^2 - 24 R2 sr \text{approx}^2 + 30 R2^2 sr \text{approx}^2 - 6 at \text{approx} c \text{approx} \gamma + 12 at \text{approx} B2 c \text{approx} \gamma + 6 c \text{approx}^2 \gamma - 12 B2 c \text{approx}^2 \gamma + 10 c \text{approx} sr \text{approx} \gamma - 20 B2 c \text{approx} sr \text{approx} \gamma - 20 c \text{approx} R2 sr \text{approx} \gamma + 40 B2 c \text{approx} R2 sr \text{approx} \gamma + 12 at \text{approx} c \text{approx} T2 \gamma - 24 at \text{approx} B2 c \text{approx} T2 \gamma + 3 c \text{approx}^2 \gamma^2 - 24 B2 c \text{approx}^2 \gamma^2 + 30 B2^2 c \text{approx}^2 \gamma^2 + 2 sb \text{approx} (5 (-1 + 2 B2) (-1 + 2 R2) sr \text{approx} + 6 (1 - 5 B2 + 5 B2^2) c \text{approx} \gamma) - 2 ab \text{approx} (2 B2^2 (4 + 7 R2) (sb \text{approx} + c \text{approx} \gamma) + R2 (3 sb \text{approx} + (3 - 5 R2) sr \text{approx} + 3 c \text{approx} \gamma) - B2 ((5 + 14 R2) sb \text{approx} + (3 - 10 R2) sr \text{approx} + c \text{approx} (5 + 14 R2) \gamma))) / . \{at \text{approx} \rightarrow at, ab \text{approx} \rightarrow ab, sr \text{approx} \rightarrow sr, c \text{approx} \rightarrow c, st \text{approx} \rightarrow st, sb \text{approx} \rightarrow sb, m \text{approx} \rightarrow m\} \right]$$

$$\text{Out[*]} = \frac{1}{8} ab (-1 + B2) B2 (-1 + R2) R2$$

$$\left(ab^2 (R2^2 - B2 R2 (3 + 7 R2) + B2^2 (4 + 7 R2 + 7 R2^2)) + 3 (1 - 8 B2 + 10 B2^2) sb^2 + 3 sr^2 - 24 R2 sr^2 + 30 R2^2 sr^2 - 6 at c \gamma + 12 at B2 c \gamma + 6 c^2 \gamma - 12 B2 c^2 \gamma + 10 c sr \gamma - 20 B2 c sr \gamma - 20 c R2 sr \gamma + 40 B2 c R2 sr \gamma + 12 at c T2 \gamma - 24 at B2 c T2 \gamma + 3 c^2 \gamma^2 - 24 B2 c^2 \gamma^2 + 30 B2^2 c^2 \gamma^2 + 2 sb (5 (-1 + 2 B2) (-1 + 2 R2) sr + 6 (1 - 5 B2 + 5 B2^2) c \gamma) - 2 ab (2 B2^2 (4 + 7 R2) (sb + c \gamma) + R2 (3 sb + (3 - 5 R2) sr + 3 c \gamma) - B2 ((5 + 14 R2) sb + (3 - 10 R2^2) sr + c (5 + 14 R2) \gamma)) \right)$$

$$\text{In[*]} := \text{Simplify} \left[\left(\frac{1}{4} (ab^2 (R2^2 - B2 * R2 (3 + 7 R2) + B2^2 * (4 + 7 * R2 (1 + R2))) + 3 sb^2 (1 - 2 B2 (4 - 5 B2)) + 3 sr^2 (1 - 2 R2 (4 - 5 R2)) - c * \gamma ((1 - 2 B2) (6 at (1 - 2 T2) - 10 sr (1 - 2 R2) - 6 c) - 3 c * \gamma (1 - 2 B2 (4 - 5 B2))) + 2 sb (5 (1 - 2 B2) (1 - 2 R2) sr + 6 c * \gamma (1 - 5 B2 (1 - B2))) - 2 ab ((sb + c * \gamma) (B2 (8 B2 - 5) + R2 (3 - 14 B2 (1 - B2))) + sr (B2 (10 R2^2 - 3) + R2 (3 - 5 R2))) \right) == \left(\frac{1}{4} (ab^2 (R2^2 - B2 R2 (3 + 7 R2) + B2^2 (4 + 7 R2 + 7 R2^2)) + 3 (1 - 8 B2 + 10 B2^2) sb^2 + 3 sr^2 - 24 R2 sr^2 + 30 R2^2 sr^2 - 6 at c \gamma + 12 at B2 c \gamma + 6 c^2 \gamma - 12 B2 c^2 \gamma + 10 c sr \gamma - 20 B2 c sr \gamma - 20 c R2 sr \gamma + 40 B2 c R2 sr \gamma + 12 at c T2 \gamma - 24 at B2 c T2 \gamma + 3 c^2 \gamma^2 - 24 B2 c^2 \gamma^2 + 30 B2^2 c^2 \gamma^2 + 2 sb (5 (-1 + 2 B2) (-1 + 2 R2) sr + 6 (1 - 5 B2 + 5 B2^2) c \gamma) - 2 ab (2 B2^2 (4 + 7 R2) (sb + c \gamma) + R2 (3 sb + (3 - 5 R2) sr + 3 c \gamma) - B2 ((5 + 14 R2) sb + (3 - 10 R2^2) sr + c (5 + 14 R2) \gamma)) \right) \right]$$

Out[*] = True

$$\frac{1}{4} (ab^2 (B2^2 (7 (R2 + 1) R2 + 4) - B2 R2 (7 R2 + 3) + R2^2) - 2 ab (((3 - 14 B2 (1 - B2)) R2 + (8 B2 - 5) B2) (c \gamma + sb) + sr (B2 (10 R2^2 - 3) + R2 (3 - 5 R2))) - c \gamma ((1 - 2 B2) (6 at (1 - 2 T2) - 6 c - 10 (1 - 2 R2) sr) - 3 (1 - 2 B2 (4 - 5 B2)) c \gamma) + 2 sb (6 (1 - 5 B2 (1 - B2)) c \gamma + 5 (1 - 2 B2) (1 - 2 R2) sr) + 3 (1 - 2 B2 (4 - 5 B2)) sb^2 + 3 (1 - 2 R2 (4 - 5 R2)) sr^2)$$

(*third-order term for DTB*)

$$\text{In[*]} := \text{Simplify} [4 m - 3 ab R2 + 6 ab B2 R2 + 3 sb - 6 B2 sb + 3 st - 6 st T2 + at (-2 + 6 T2) + c (4 + \gamma - 6 B2 \gamma) == 3 ((1 - 2 B2) (sb - ab * R2) + (1 - 2 T2) st) - 2 at (1 - 3 T2) + c (4 + \gamma (1 - 6 B2)) + 4 m]$$

Out[*] = True

$$\frac{1}{2} (3 ((1 - 2 B2) (sb - ab R2) + st (1 - 2 T2)) - 2 at (1 - 3 T2) + c ((1 - 6 B2) \gamma + 4) + 4 m)$$

(*expression for DTBR*)

$$\text{In[*]} := \text{Simplify} \left[\frac{2}{3} ab at B2 (1 - 3 B2 + 2 B2^2) c (-1 + R2) R2 (-1 + T2) T2 \gamma == \left(\frac{2}{3} * ab * at * c * \gamma * (1 - T2) T2 (1 - R2) R2 (1 - B2) B2 (1 - 2 B2) \right) \right]$$

Out[*] = True

Visual inspection of the linkage expressions

(*for consistency with weak selection assumptions,
find a set of small parameter values that still
meets the criteria for an internal T2 equilibrium*)

(*The T2=Teq equilibrium is stable as long as at >

$$-1 + \frac{1+m}{(-1+m)(-1+st)} \text{ and } 0 < c < \frac{at-2m-atm+(1+at)(-1+m)st}{at+2m+atm+st-mst} .*)$$

```
In[*]:= Manipulate[{{-1 + \frac{1+m}{(-1+m)(-1+st)}, \frac{at-2m-atm+(1+at)(-1+m)st}{at+2m+atm+st-mst}},
  {{m, 0.0001}, 0, 1}, {{st, 0.001}, 0, 1}, {{at, 0.002}, -1 + \frac{1+m}{(-1+m)(-1+st)}, 30}]
```

The screenshot shows a Mathematica Manipulate interface. On the left, there are three sliders labeled 'm', 'st', and 'at'. The 'm' slider is set to approximately 0.0001, 'st' to 0.001, and 'at' to 0.002. Below the sliders, a text box displays the output: {0.00120122, 0.249336}. There is a '+' icon in the top right corner of the interface.

```
In[160]:= ClearAll[m, st, c, at, ab, sb, sr, T2, R2, B2]
```

```
In[162]:= Teq = \frac{1 - m + \frac{2(1+c+at)c}{st+c}m}{1+m} /. {m -> 0.0001, st -> 0.001, c -> 0.001, at -> 0.002}
```

Out[162]= 0.798614

(*look at expression for DBR*)

```

In[ ]:= Manipulate[Plot[ $\left(\frac{1}{8} ab (-1 + B2) B2 (-1 + R2) R2$ 
(4 + 2 ab R2 - 4 ab B2 (1 + R2) + ab2 (R22 - B2 R2 (3 + 7 R2) + B22 (4 + 7 R2 + 7 R22)) +
3 (1 - 8 B2 + 10 B22) sb2 + 3 sr2 - 24 R2 sr2 + 30 R22 sr2 - 6 at c  $\gamma$  +
12 at B2 c  $\gamma$  + 6 c2  $\gamma$  - 12 B2 c2  $\gamma$  + 10 c sr  $\gamma$  - 20 B2 c sr  $\gamma$  - 20 c R2 sr  $\gamma$  +
40 B2 c R2 sr  $\gamma$  + 12 at c T2  $\gamma$  - 24 at B2 c T2  $\gamma$  + 3 c2  $\gamma$ 2 - 24 B2 c2  $\gamma$ 2 +
30 B22 c2  $\gamma$ 2 - 6 (sb - 2 B2 sb + sr - 2 R2 sr + (1 - 2 B2) c  $\gamma$ ) +
2 sb (5 (-1 + 2 B2) (-1 + 2 R2) sr + 6 (1 - 5 B2 + 5 B22) c  $\gamma$ ) -
2 ab (2 B22 (4 + 7 R2) (sb + c  $\gamma$ ) + R2 (3 sb + (3 - 5 R2) sr + 3 c  $\gamma$ ) -
B2 ((5 + 14 R2) sb + (3 - 10 R22) sr + c (5 + 14 R2)  $\gamma$ )) /.\frac{1 - m + \frac{2(1+c+at)c}{st+c} \frac{m}{st+at(-1+c+st)}}{1+m} /. {m → 0.0001, st → 0.001}}],
{ $\gamma$ , 0, 1}, PlotRange → Full], {{R2, 0.5},
0,
1}, {{B2, 0.5},
0,
1}, {c,
0.001,
 $\frac{at - 2m - at m + (1 + at) (-1 + m) st}{at + 2m + at m + st - m st}$  /.
{m → 0.0001, st → 0.001}},
{{at, 0.002}, 0, 16}, {ab, 0, 20}]

```


In[]:= dbrplot =

```
GraphicsRow[Table[Plot[
$$\left(\frac{1}{8} ab (-1 + B2) B2 (-1 + R2) R2 (4 + 2 ab R2 - 4 ab B2 (1 + R2) + ab^2 (R2^2 - B2 R2 (3 + 7 R2) + B2^2 (4 + 7 R2 + 7 R2^2)) + 3 (1 - 8 B2 + 10 B2^2) sb^2 + 3 sr^2 - 24 R2 sr^2 + 30 R2^2 sr^2 - 6 at c \gamma + 12 at B2 c \gamma + 6 c^2 \gamma - 12 B2 c^2 \gamma + 10 c sr \gamma - 20 B2 c sr \gamma - 20 c R2 sr \gamma + 40 B2 c R2 sr \gamma + 12 at c T2 \gamma - 24 at B2 c T2 \gamma + 3 c^2 \gamma^2 - 24 B2 c^2 \gamma^2 + 30 B2^2 c^2 \gamma^2 - 6 (sb - 2 B2 sb + sr - 2 R2 sr + (1 - 2 B2) c \gamma) + 2 sb (5 (-1 + 2 B2) (-1 + 2 R2) sr + 6 (1 - 5 B2 + 5 B2^2) c \gamma) - 2 ab (2 B2^2 (4 + 7 R2) (sb + c \gamma) + R2 (3 sb + (3 - 5 R2) sr + 3 c \gamma) - B2 ((5 + 14 R2) sb + (3 - 10 R2^2) sr + c (5 + 14 R2) \gamma))\right) / .$$

{sr → 0.00001, st → 0.001, sb → 0.001, m → 0.0001, T2 → 0.7986137064685491, R2 → 0.5, B2 → 0.5, c → 0.001, at → 0.002}],
{γ, 0, 1}, PlotRange → Full, PlotStyle → {Thick, Black},
Frame → True,
FrameStyle →
{{{16, Black, FontFamily → "Times"}, {18, Black, FontFamily → "Times"}},
{{16, Black, FontFamily → "Times"}, {18, Black, FontFamily → "Times"}}},
FrameLabel → {{Text[Style[ Row[{Subscript["D", "BR"] , " approx"}],
FontFamily → "Times", FontSize → 22, Black]], None},
{Text[Style["Effectiveness of Protection, γ", FontFamily → "Times",
FontSize → 20]], Text[Style[ Row[{Subscript["a", "b"] , "=" , ab}],
FontFamily → "Times", FontSize → 22, Black]]}},
{ab, {0.001, 0.003, 0.005}}, ImageSize → 1440]
```



```
In[ ]:= Export["Figure_S2.pdf", dbrplot];
```

In[]:= dbrplotc =

```
GraphicsRow[Table[Plot[
$$\left[ \frac{1}{8} ab (-1 + B2) B2 (-1 + R2) R2 (4 + 2 ab R2 - 4 ab B2 (1 + R2) + ab^2 (R2^2 - B2 R2 (3 + 7 R2) + B2^2 (4 + 7 R2 + 7 R2^2)) + 3 (1 - 8 B2 + 10 B2^2) sb^2 + 3 sr^2 - 24 R2 sr^2 + 30 R2^2 sr^2 - 6 at c \gamma + 12 at B2 c \gamma + 6 c^2 \gamma - 12 B2 c^2 \gamma + 10 c sr \gamma - 20 B2 c sr \gamma - 20 c R2 sr \gamma + 40 B2 c R2 sr \gamma + 12 at c T2 \gamma - 24 at B2 c T2 \gamma + 3 c^2 \gamma^2 - 24 B2 c^2 \gamma^2 + 30 B2^2 c^2 \gamma^2 - 6 (sb - 2 B2 sb + sr - 2 R2 sr + (1 - 2 B2) c \gamma) + 2 sb (5 (-1 + 2 B2) (-1 + 2 R2) sr + 6 (1 - 5 B2 + 5 B2^2) c \gamma) - 2 ab (2 B2^2 (4 + 7 R2) (sb + c \gamma) + R2 (3 sb + (3 - 5 R2) sr + 3 c \gamma) - B2 ((5 + 14 R2) sb + (3 - 10 R2^2) sr + c (5 + 14 R2) \gamma)) \right] /. \{sr \rightarrow 0.00001, st \rightarrow 0.001, sb \rightarrow 0.001, m \rightarrow 0.0001, T2 \rightarrow \frac{1 - m + \frac{2 (1+c+at c) m}{st+c st+at (-1+c+st)}}{1 + m} /. \{m \rightarrow 0.0001, st \rightarrow 0.001, at \rightarrow 0.002\}, R2 \rightarrow 0.5, B2 \rightarrow 0.5, ab \rightarrow 0.005, at \rightarrow 0.002\} \right], \{\gamma, 0, 1\}, PlotRange \rightarrow Full, PlotStyle \rightarrow \{Thick, Black\}, Frame \rightarrow True, FrameStyle \rightarrow \{\{16, Black, FontFamily \rightarrow "Times"\}, \{18, Black, FontFamily \rightarrow "Times"\}\}, \{\{16, Black, FontFamily \rightarrow "Times"\}, \{18, Black, FontFamily \rightarrow "Times"\}\}, FrameLabel \rightarrow \{\{Text[Style[ Row[{Subscript["D", "BR"] , " approx"}], FontFamily \rightarrow "Times", FontSize \rightarrow 22, Black]], None\}, \{Text[Style["Effectiveness of Protection, \gamma"], FontFamily \rightarrow "Times", FontSize \rightarrow 20]], Text[Style[ Row[{Style["c", FontSlant \rightarrow Italic] , "=", c}], FontFamily \rightarrow "Times", FontSize \rightarrow 22, Black]}\}], \{c, \{0.001, 0.003, 0.005\}\}, ImageSize \rightarrow 1440]$$

```

Out[]:=


```
In[*]:= Export["Figure_S2_b.pdf", dbrplotc];
```

```
(*look at expression for DTB*)
```

```
Manipulate[
```

```
Plot[- $\frac{1}{2}$  at (-1 + B2) B2 c (-1 + T2) T2  $\gamma$  (-2 + 4 m - 3 ab R2 + 6 ab B2 R2 + 3 sb - 6 B2 sb +
      3 st - 6 st T2 + at (-2 + 6 T2) + c (4 +  $\gamma$  - 6 B2  $\gamma$ )) /.
      {sr -> 0.01, st -> 0.1, sb -> 0.1, m -> 0.1, T2 -> 0.9}, { $\gamma$ , 0, 1}, PlotRange -> Full],
      {{R2, 0.5}, 0, 1}, {{B2, 0.5}, 0, 1}, {c, 0.2, 0.6},
      {{at, 12}, 4, 16}, {ab, 0, 20}]
```



```
Out[*]:=
```